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The new records of Calliphoridae and Sarcophagidae (Diptera) from Myrhorod, Poltava Region, Ukraine

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Verves, Yu. G., Khrokalo, L. A. & Verves, K. Yu. The new records of Calliphoridae and Sarcophagidae (Diptera) from Myrhorod, Poltava Region, Ukraine. Summary. As a results of authors' field studies, thirteen species of Calliphoridae and nineteen of Sarcophagidae were collected in Myrhorod City for the first time. Twenty-nine species of calliphorids and eighty-four species of sarcophagids (113 in total) have been recorded from Poltava Region. Among them, one *Phormia regina* is recorded from Poltava Region for the first time. The total number (113) consists at least 80–90% of the full regional faunistic list.

Key words: Diptera, Calliphoridae, Sarcophagidae, Ukraine, Poltava Region, Myrhorod, fauna.

Вервес, Ю. Г., Хрокало, Л. А. і Вервес, К. Ю. Нові знахідки Calliphoridae та Sarcophagidae (Diptera) в Миргороді Полтавської області. Резюме. Внаслідок польових досліджень авторів 17–24.07.2020, вперше для міста Миргород зібрано 13 видів Calliphoridae та 19 – Sarcophagidae. 29 видів каліфорид та 84 видів саркофагид відомі для Полтавської області загалом. З них один вид (*Phormia regina*) вперше вказаний для Полтавщини. Ця цифра (113) становить не менш ніж 80–90% повного регіонального фауністичного списку.

Ключові слова: Diptera, Calliphoridae, Sarcophagidae, Україна, Полтавська область, Миргород, фауна.

Introduction

Altogether 74 species of Calliphoridae and 180 species of Sarcophagidae have been reported from Ukraine (Verves & Khrokalo, 2018). Regional faunas of Poltava Region include 29 species of Calliphoridae (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010; present data) and 84 species¹ of Sarcophagidae (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b; 2018). This number is estimated as 80–90% of the full regional faunistic lists.

Material and methods

The material was collected by sweeping net from 17th to 24th July, 2020 on mesophitic meadows with shrubs along Khorol River, 49°59'N, 33°36'E, 100–110 m a. s. l. (fig. 1).

Nomenclature of taxa follows Rognes & Pape (2007); Verves & Khrokalo (2006) (Calliphoridae) and Povolný &

¹ Altogether in both papers.

Verves (1997); Verves (1986, 1990); Verves & Khrokalo (2006b) (Sarcophagidae). 282 specimens from 13 species of Calliphoridae and 198 specimens from 19 species of Sarcophagidae were collected by entomological net and identified after reliable keys (Calliphoridae: Grunin, 1970; Rognes, 1991; and Sarcophagidae: Povolný & Verves, 1997; Rohdendorf, 1970; Verves, 1982, 1985, 1993; Verves & Khrokalo, 2006b; Zerova et al., 2006). All the specimens from this study are deposited in the collection of Institute for Evolutionary Ecology, Kyiv.

Results and discussion

Thirty-one species of both families are collected and recorded from Myrhorod City for the first time, and *Phormia regina* is a new record for Poltava Region.

Fig. 1. Collecting locality: Khorol River bank in the Myrhorod City, about 110 m a. s. l. (49°58'34" N, 33°36'19" E), 24.vii.2020 (photo by Yu. Verves).

List of Calliphoridae and Sarcophagidae known for Poltava Region

Lists of 29 calliphorid species and 84 sarcophagid species from Poltava Region are compiled as a result of our own collecting and analysis of literature data.

Calliphoridae

Bellardia bayeri (Jacentkovský, 1937)

Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 7♂. Total: 7 specimens (Yu. Verves).

Bellardia pandia (Walker, 1849)

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Bellardia stricta (Villeneuve, 1926)

Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Calliphora loewi Enderlein, 1903

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Calliphora vicina Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 2♂, 1♀. Total: 3 specimens (Yu. Verves).

Calliphora vomitoria (Linnaeus, 1758)

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Cynomya mortuorum (Linnaeus, 1761)

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Lucilia (Bufolucilia) bufonivora Moniez, 1876

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 1♂, 1♀. Total: 2 specimens (Yu. Verves).

Lucilia (Bufolucilia) silvarum (Meigen, 1826)

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River,

49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 7♂.
Total: 7 specimens (Yu. Verves).

Lucilia (s. str.) caesar (Linnaeus, 1758)

Ramazanov, 1998; Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010; Viktorov-Nabokov, 1959, 1963, 1968.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 32♂, 4♀. Total: 36 specimens (Yu. Verves).

Lucilia (s. str.) illustris (Meigen, 1826)

Ramazanov, 1998; Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Lucilia (s. str.) pilosiventris Kramer, 1910

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Lucilia (s. str.) richardsi Collin, 1926

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Lucilia (s. str.) sericata (Meigen, 1826)

Ramazanov, 1998; Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010; Viktorov-Nabokov, 1959, 1963, 1968.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 5♂, 2♀. Total: 7 specimens (Yu. Verves).

Melinda viridicyanea (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Phormia regina (Meigen, 1826)

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 21♂.
Total: 21 specimens (Yu. Verves).

First record from Poltava Region.

Protocalliphora azurea (Fallén, 1917)

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Protophormia terraenovae (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010; Viktorov-Nabokov, 1959.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 1♂, 1♀. Total: 2 specimens (Yu. Verves).

Eurychaeta palpalis (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)

Verves, 1982, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Pollenia amentaria (Scopoli, 1763)

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Pollenia angustigena Wainwright, 1940

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 33♂.
Total: 33 specimens (Yu. Verves).

Pollenia atramentaria (Meigen, 1826)

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Pollenia griseotomentosa (Jacentkovský, 1944)

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 7♂.
Total: 7 specimens (Yu. Verves).

Pollenia hungarica Rognes, 1987

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 80♂, 1♀. Total: 81 specimens (Yu. Verves).

Pollenia labialis Robineau-Desvoidy, 1863

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Pollenia pediculata Macquart, 1834

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 2♂.
Total: 2 specimens (Yu. Verves).

Pollenia rudis (Fabricius, 1794)

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 74♂, 1♀. Total: 75 specimens (Yu. Verves).

Pollenia tenuiforceps Séguy, 1928

Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Stomorphina lunata (Fabricius, 1805)

Grunin, 1970; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010.

Sarcophagidae***Macronychia* (s. str.) *striginervis* (Zetterstedt, 1838)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2006b, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Macronychia* (*Moschusa*) *griseola* (Fallén, 1820)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2006b, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Macronychia* (*Moschusa*) *polyodon* (Meigen, 1824)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2006b, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Senotainia* (*Arrenopus*) *albifrons* (Rondani, 1859)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Senotainia* (*Arrenopus*) *sibirica* Rohdendorf, 1935**

Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 1 ♀. Total: 1 specimen (Yu. Verves).

***Senotainia* (s. str.) *conica* (Fallén, 1810)**

Stackelberg, 1962; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 1 ♂. Total: 1 specimen (Yu. Verves).

***Senotainia* (s. str.) *rossica* Rohdendorf, 1935**

Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Senotainia* (s. str.) *tricuspis* (Meigen, 1838)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Pterella* *grisea* (Meigen, 1824)**

Stackelberg, 1962; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Pterella* *melanura* (Meigen, 1824)**

Stackelberg, 1962; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Anacanthothecum* *testaceifrons* (Roser, 1840)**

Stackelberg, 1962; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Miltogramma* *germari* Meigen, 1824**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Miltogramma* *murina* Meigen, 1824**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Miltogramma* *oestracea* (Fallén, 1820)**

Stackelberg, 1962; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Miltogramma* *punctata* Meigen, 1824**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Miltogrammidium* *rutilans* (Meigen, 1824)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Ptychoneura* *minuta* (Gallen, 1810)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Amobia* *signata* (Meigen, 1824)**

Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Yaroshevsky, 1882.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 1 ♀. Total: 1 specimen (Yu. Verves).

***Phylloteles* *pictipennis* Löw, 1844**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Mesomelena* *mesomelaena* (Löw, 1848)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Ptychoneura* *minuta* (Fallén, 1810)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Metopia* *argentata* Macquart, 1850**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Metopia* *argyrocephala* (Meigen, 1824)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Metopia* *campestris* (Fallén, 1810)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Yaroshevsky, 1882; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Metopia* *staegerii* Rondani, 1859**

Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a.

***Phrosinella* (s. str.) *nasuta* (Meigen, 1824)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Hilarella* *hilarella* (Zetterstedt, 1844)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Hilarella stictica* (Meigen, 1830)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Paragusia elegantula* (Zetterstedt, 1844)**

Stackelberg, 1962; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Taxigramma heteroneura* (Meigen, 1830)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Nyctia halterata* (Panzer, 1798)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a; Zerova et al., 2006.

***Agria affinis* (Fallén, 1817)**

Khitsova, 1978; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a.

***Agria mamillata* (Pandellé, 1896)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a.

***Angiometopa falleni* Pape, 1986**

Stackelberg, 1962; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a.

***Brachicoma devia* (Fallén, 1820)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a.

***Sarcophila latifrons* (Fallén, 1817)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a.

***Sarcophila meridionalis* Rohdendorf & Verves, 1982**

Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a.

***Wohlfahrtia intermedia* (Portschinsky, 1887)**

Portschinsky, 1916; Rohdendorf, 1956; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a.

***Wohlfahrtia magnifica* (Schiner, 1862)**

Portschinsky, 1916; Rohdendorf, 1956; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a.

***Wohlfahrtia meigeni* (Schiner, 1862)**

Verves, 1975, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a.

***Blaesoxipha cochlearis* (Pandellé, 1896)**

Rohdendorf, 1937; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Blaesoxipha laticornis* (Meigen, 1826)**

Stackelberg, 1962; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Blaesoxipha litoralis* (Villeneuve, 1911)**

Rohdendorf, 1937; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Blaesoxipha redempta* (Pandellé, 1896)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Blaesoxipha unicolor* (Villeneuve, 1912)**

Stackelberg, 1962; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Servaisia* (s. str.) *rossica* (Villeneuve, 1912)**

Rohdendorf, 1937; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Tephromyia grisea* (Meigen, 1826)**

Portschinsky, 1916; Rohdendorf, 1956; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a.

***Sarcotachinella sinuata* (Meigen, 1826)**

Rohdendorf, 1937; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 4♂. Total: 4 specimens (Yu. Verves).

***Ravinia pernix* (Harris, 1780)**

Rohdendorf, 1937; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b; Viktorov-Nabokov, 1959, 1963, 1968.

***Helicophagella* (s. str.) *agnata* (Rondani, 1860)**

Rohdendorf, 1937; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Helicophagella* (s. str.) *crassimargo* (Pandellé, 1896)**

Rohdendorf, 1937; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Helicophagella* (*Parabellieria*) *macrura* (Rohdendorf, 1937)**

Rohdendorf, 1937; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Helicophagella* (*Parabellieria*) *melanura* (Meigen, 1826)**

Verves, 1974, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b; Viktorov-Nabokov, 1963.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 28♂, 1♀. Total: 29 specimens (Yu. Verves).

***Heteronychia* (s. str.) *bulgarica* (Enderlein, 1936)**

Rohdendorf, 1937; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 2♂. Total: 2 specimens (Yu. Verves).

***Heteronychia* (s. str.) *depressifrons* (Zetterstedt, 1845)**

Rohdendorf, 1937; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Heteronychia* (s. str.) *dissimilis* (Meigen, 1826)**

Rohdendorf, 1937; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Heteronychia* (s. str.) *haemorrhoea* (Meigen, 1826)**

Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Heteronychia* (s. str.) *haemorrhoides* (Böttcher, 1913)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 1♂, 2♀. Total: 3 specimens (Yu. Verves).

***Heteronychia* (s. str.) *mazurmovitshi* Verves, 1979**

Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Heteronychia* (s. str.) *proxima* (Rondani, 1860)**

Rohdendorf, 1937; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Heteronychia* (s. str.) *vagans* (Meigen, 1826)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Asceloctella* (*Mimarhopocnemis*) *granulata* (Kramer, 1908)**

Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Bellieriomima* *subulata* (Pandellé, 1896)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Myorhina* (*Mehria*) *nemoralis* (Kramer, 1908)**

Rohdendorf, 1937; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Myorhina* (s. str.) *socrus* (Rondani, 1860)**

Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Thyrsoctema* *incisilobata* (Pandellé, 1896)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 6♂. Total: 6 specimens (Yu. Verves).

***Bercaea* *africa* (Wiedemann, 1824)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 1♂. Total: 1 specimen (Yu. Verves).

***Liopygia* (*Jantia*) *crassipalpis* (Macquart, 1839)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Liopygia* (*Thomsonia*) *argyrostoma* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Liosarcophaga* (s. str.) *emdeni* (Rohdendorf, 1969)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 7♂. Total: 7 specimens (Yu. Verves).

***Liosarcophaga* (s. str.) *harpax* (Pandellé, 1896)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Liosarcophaga* (s. str.) *parkeri* (Rohdendorf, 1937)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 31♂. Total: 31 specimens (Yu. Verves).

***Liosarcophaga* (s. str.) *portschinskyi* (Rohdendorf, 1937)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 5♂. Total: 5 specimens (Yu. Verves).

***Liosarcophaga* (s. str.) *tuberosa* (Pandellé, 1896)**

Rohdendorf, 1937; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 3♂. Total: 3 specimens (Yu. Verves).

***Liosarcophaga* (*Pandelleisca*) *similis* (Meade, 1876)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 7♂. Total: 7 specimens (Yu. Verves).

***Parasarcophaga* (s. str.) *albiceps* (Meigen, 1826)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 2♂. Total: 2 specimens (Yu. Verves).

***Robineauella* (s. str.) *caerulescens* (Zetterstedt, 1838)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Kramerea schuetzei* (Kramer, 1909)**

Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Rosellea aratrix* (Pandellé, 1896)**

Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Sarcophaga carnaria* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 6♂. Total: 6 specimens (Yu. Verves).

***Sarcophaga lehmanni* Müller, 1922**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 49♂. Total: 49 specimens (Yu. Verves).

***Sarcophaga subvicina* Rohdendorf, 1937**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Sarcophaga ukrainica* Rohdendorf, 1937**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

***Sarcophaga variegata* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b.

Material examined. Ukraine, Poltava Region, mesophitic meadows with bushes along Khorol River, 49.9833, 33.6000, 100–110 m a. s. l., 17–24.07.2020, 37♂. Total: 37 specimens (Yu. Verves).

The number of 113 species from both families is estimated to consist at least 80–90% of distinct regional biodiversity of Poltava Region in general, but full faunistic list for Myrhorod City territory is not known more about 25–30%.

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